

D1.3 Data Management Plan M18

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Abbreviations

CC	Creative Commons
CSV	Comma-Separated Value
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC SB	EOSC Steering Board
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
M	Month
PID	Persistent Identifier

Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EOSC Track project outlines the strategies and procedures for managing the data generated, collected, and processed throughout the project's duration. The DMP ensures that all research data are handled following best practices for data management, facilitating the accessibility, preservation, and reuse of data. This is the second, updated version of the DMP. It has been created using the ARGOS service (<https://argos.openaire.eu>), an online tool for creating, managing, and sharing DMPs and linking them with the research artifacts they correspond to.

Introduction

The EOSC Track project will develop and operate the EOSC Open Science Observatory, a policy intelligence tool that will monitor policies, investments, digital research outputs, skills, and infrastructure. EOSC Track's mission is to simplify and streamline monitoring in the European Open Science ecosystem, to bring a common understanding of collecting and interpreting data appropriate for monitoring, and to assist policymakers and research executives across Europe in understanding, shaping, and aligning policies and implementation. Given the complexity and scope of the EOSC Track, a well-defined release and deployment strategy is essential to ensure that newly developed features are systematically tested, validated, and integrated into the live environment in a controlled and secure manner, minimising risks and maximising operational readiness.

The primary objective of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to outline the strategies and procedures for managing the data generated, collected, and processed throughout the EOSC Track project's duration. The DMP ensures that all research data are handled in accordance with best practices for data management, facilitating accessibility, preservation, and reuse of data. The ARGOS service (<https://argos.openaire.eu>), an online tool for creating, managing, and sharing DMPs, has been used to create this DMP. This is the second version of the DMP. It is still a living document that will be updated as necessary.

The updated version includes detailed resource allocations for each dataset, along with updates to the EOSC Steering Board Survey data and the addition of datasets related to CoARA signatories. Thus, in this DMP, there are four data sets described: from the EOSC SB Survey, the OpenAIRE Graph Dataset, data from Eurostat and data on CoARA signatories.

The numbering of the questions follows the structure by ARGOS service to allow the updating of the DMP in the future (i.e., filling out questions for which the information is currently missing).

Powered by

Data Management Plan

A) EOSC Steering Board Survey Data

The EOSC Track project will generate primary data through the EOSC Steering Board Survey (EOSC SB Survey). This survey is essential for collecting information directly from stakeholders involved in the EOSC. This primary data is critical for developing reliable indicators and insights into the current state and progress of open science initiatives.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

Data Generation:

The EOSC Track project will generate primary data through the EOSC SB Survey. This survey is essential for collecting information directly from stakeholders involved in the EOSC. The data collected will include responses on various aspects of open science practices, the FAIRness of data, and reproducibility metrics. This primary data is critical for developing reliable indicators and insights into the current state and progress of open science initiatives.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

The dataset from the EOSC SB Survey is primarily observational data. This type of data is collected directly from EOSC members community through structured survey instruments.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

The data from the EOSC SB Survey will be collected, processed, and stored in the following digital formats:

Primary Format: CSV (Comma-Separated Values): This is the primary format for storing raw survey data. CSV is a widely accepted and easily readable format that facilitates data sharing and interoperability across various platforms and software

Additional Formats: JSON (JavaScript Object Notation): For structured data storage and transmission, especially when integrating with web applications and APIs. JSON is lightweight and human-readable, making it suitable for data exchange between systems.

XML (eXtensible Markup Language): For complex data representation and when a more flexible data structure is required. XML is widely used for data interchange between different systems and platforms.

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

10 MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- The public

The dataset from the EOSC SB Survey will be useful to stakeholders such as the EOSC Steering Board, EOSC-A, EOSC-A Task Forces, National Open Access Desks (NOADs), representatives of EOSC-related projects, National Points of Reference for STI, ERA Representatives, CONOSC, ESFRI KPI Group, E-Infras and Science Clusters, National OS Monitoring Systems, and scholarly communication researchers / STI evaluation experts; partners including PathOS, EU Node, GraspOS, OSTrills, CoARA, OPUS, and other relevant EU-funded projects; end-users such as researchers, research funding organizations (RFOs), research performing organizations (RPOs), policymakers, and research administrators; and the general public including citizens interested in open science, media, and educational institutions.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

<https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

ROR

Cordis

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

- OpenAIRE Guidelines
- DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 WHAT TYPE(S) OF METADATA?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Legal

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

Yes

The metadata for the EOSC SB Survey dataset will use standardized vocabularies in accordance with the DataCite Metadata Schema and OpenAIRE guidelines. This ensures greater interoperability across systems and enhances the discoverability, reusability, and integration of the dataset within various research infrastructures and platforms.

3.1.1.5 PLEASE PROVIDE URL/DESCRIPTION OF USED VOCABULARIES

<https://support.datacite.org/docs/glossary-of-commonly-used-terms>

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.1.1.7 HOW ARE SEARCHABLE METADATA PROVIDED?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

Yes

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

Data of Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2023 (v0.2):
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130643>

Data of Analysis of Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science
2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130172>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards

- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Data of Survey on National Contributions to EOSC 2023

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Publication of Data: Survey data will be published in accordance with the OpenAIRE Argos DMP service, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles. The data will be well-described using standardized metadata, properly documented, and associated with Persistent Identifiers, under CC 4.0 license.

Access via APIs: The dataset will be accessible through standard/documented APIs, facilitating integration with other systems and tools. This enables users to programmatically access the data for analysis and integration into other platforms.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

The datasets deposited in open repositories (Zenodo) will be preserved for long-term access. This ensures that the data remains accessible and usable beyond the duration of the project.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

All dataset will be open, under Creative Commons 4.0.

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

The metadata for the EOSC SB Survey dataset will use standardized vocabularies in accordance with the DataCite Metadata Schema and OpenAIRE guidelines. This ensures greater interoperability across systems and enhances the discoverability, reusability, and integration of the dataset within various research infrastructures and platforms.

<https://support.datacite.org/docs/glossary-of-commonly-used-terms>

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

Yes

OpenAIRE Guidelines

3.3.7 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT PROVIDE QUALIFIED REFERENCES WITH OTHER OUTPUTS?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 WHAT REUSABILITY AND / OR REPRODUCIBILITY METHODS ARE FOLLOWED?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

10000 Euro, paid from the direct cost of the project.

The EOSC Steering Board Survey dataset requires substantial manual effort to ensure it meets FAIR standards. Activities include:

- Cleaning and validating responses, many of which are open text and require contextual interpretation;
- Standardising and annotating metadata for long-term findability and reuse;
- Anonymizing sensitive input where applicable, in compliance with GDPR and ethical standards;
- Depositing the dataset in an open repository with persistent identifiers and reuse licenses.

These activities demand dedicated staff time and coordination with national authorities, justifying a direct cost estimate of EUR 10,000 for complete FAIRification and publication.

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

Other

By the EOSC Track project Budget.

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

Tereza Szybisty (Simova) (orcid:0000-0002-1774-4335)

Tereza Szybisty (Simova) is EOSC Track project manager, responsible for overall implantation of DMP.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 WHAT SECURITY MEASURES ARE FOLLOWED?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 WHAT CONDITIONS DO THE SECURITY MEASURES MEET?

- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery

5.1.3 HOW WILL YOU PRESERVE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE LONG TERM?

The dataset will be deposited in Zenodo, an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. Zenodo provides a reliable and sustainable platform for long-term data preservation.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

B) OpenAIRE Graph Dataset

The OpenAIRE Graph Dataset is a comprehensive and openly accessible dataset that represents a detailed and interconnected view of research activities and outputs across Europe and beyond. This dataset aggregates metadata from a wide range of sources, including institutional repositories, data archives, and research information systems. It includes information on publications, datasets, projects, organizations, and other research-related entities.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-LD

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

272 GB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

The data from the OpenAIRE Graph Dataset is being collected to enrich the EOSC Open Science Observatory. This comprehensive and interconnected dataset provides high-quality, accurate, and up-to-date metadata on research activities and outputs across Europe, which is essential for facilitating in-depth analysis of open science practices, trends, and impacts. Integrating this data supports the principles of open science by promoting transparency, collaboration, and innovation, and enhances the Observatory's ability to monitor and report.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Other

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

DOI

DOI for dataset: 10.5281/zenodo.4201546

DOI for updated dataset, version 9.0.1 10.5281/zenodo.14851262

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

Yes

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up

- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

The datasets deposited in open repositories (Zenodo) will be preserved for long-term access. This ensures that the data remains accessible and usable beyond the duration of the project.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.3.2 IF YOU CREATED THE VOCABULARY, WHERE CAN IT BE FOUND?

OpenAIRE documentation: <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/>

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG): <https://explore.openaire.eu/sdgs>

Fields of Science (FoS): <https://explore.openaire.eu/fields-of-science>

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

No

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

documentation: <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs>

4. Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

1000 Euro to cover storage and re-use.

Although the OpenAIRE Graph is a FAIR and openly available dataset, EOSC Track incurs indirect costs related to:

- Maintaining API connections and scripts to regularly retrieve data;
- Transforming and aligning the data with internal models;
- Embedding it in the EOSC Open Science Observatory, including harmonization and visualization.

These activities do not alter the dataset itself but represent necessary work to reuse it effectively in a consistent, user-facing environment. A modest cost of EUR 1,000 is estimated to cover these indirect technical and development tasks.

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

It will be covered by EOSC Track budget.

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

Tereza Szybisty (Simova) (orcid: [0000-0002-1774-4335](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1774-4335))

Project Lead

7.1 Other

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

C) Eurostat data

In the EOSC Open Science Observatory, we are currently using data from Eurostat about the Total Researchers by sectors of performance - full-time equivalent (i.e. Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems, and in the management of the projects concerned. FTE (Full-time equivalent) corresponds to one year's work by one person (for example, a person who devotes 40 % of his time to R&D is counted as 0.4 FTE)).

It is possible that in the future months of the project, other data from Eurostat will be used in the EOSC Open Science Observatory, thus it will become part of the EOSC Track DMP.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

The dataset from Eurostat, "Total researchers by sectors of performance - full time equivalent," is observational and secondary data. It captures empirical data on the number of researchers, measured in FTE, across various sectors. This dataset enriches the EOSC Track project by providing insights into the distribution and engagement of researchers across different sectors.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

CSV, TSV

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

19 KB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

By integrating this comprehensive and standardized data, the EOSC Open Science Observatory can offer more detailed and accurate insights into research and development activities within the EU. This, in turn, supports the EOSC Open Science Observatory's objectives of monitoring and reporting on the state of open science, enhancing data quality, and providing valuable metrics for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders involved in advancing open science practices.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

<https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

- Data identifiers
- National identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

The metadata are already provided by Eurostat (see https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/rd_esms.htm for more)

3.1.1.5 PLEASE PROVIDE URL/DESCRIPTION OF USED VOCABULARIES

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/rd_esms.htm

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Eurostat

Eurostat; Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Total researchers by sectors of performance - full time equivalent

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

No

The metadata are provided by Eurostat (see https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/rd_esms.htm for more)

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

see https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/rd_esms.htm for more

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

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4. Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

1000 Euro to cover storage and re-use.

The Eurostat data is already publicly available under FAIR principles and does not require FAIRification by EOSC Track. However, minor indirect costs are incurred to:

- Retrieve and process the data from official Eurostat APIs;
- Convert it into formats compatible with internal indicators and dashboards;

- Visualize it as part of the EOSC Open Science Observatory outputs.

These activities ensure the data remains interoperable and usable within the context of EOSC Track, justifying a modest indirect cost estimate of EUR 1,000.

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

It will be covered by EOSC Track budget.

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

Tereza Szybisty (Simova) (orcid: [0000-0002-1774-4335](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1774-4335))

Project Lead

D) CoARA Signatories Dataset

This entry documents the reuse of the CoARA signatories dataset within the EOSC Track project. The dataset, which lists institutions that have signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, is curated, owned, and maintained by the CoARA secretariat. It is publicly accessible via the official CoARA web and shared by CoARA Secretariat. The dataset remains under authority of CoARA Secretariat, with EOSC Track having no control over its licensing, modification, or redistribution.

Due to these ownership and reuse constraints, the EOSC Track project does not assign a license, does not provide metadata, and does not take active steps to make the dataset FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Instead, the data is used to inform national-level indicators in the EOSC Open Science Observatory and enrich the project's analytical outputs, with appropriate citation and source referencing.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Other

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

We are re-using the publicly available CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) signatories dataset, which provides a list of institutions and organizations that have committed to the reform of research assessment practices. The dataset is provided by the CoARA Secretariat

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

The CoARA dataset is a curated list compiled by the CoARA secretariat, aggregating institutional signatories of the agreement.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

The CoARA dataset is provided in XML format.

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

50 KB to 200 KB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

We are re-using the CoARA signatories dataset to track institutional engagement with research assessment reform, which is a relevant Open Science policy indicator. This data supports the EOSC Open Science Observatory by enabling analysis of how national ecosystems are aligning with evolving research evaluation standards.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

The dataset originates from the official CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) portal, where the list of signatory institutions is maintained and shared by the CoARA Secretariat.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY PUBLISHED DATASET?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

<https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Other

No persistent identifiers (PIDs) are assigned to this dataset. The CoARA signatories dataset is curated and controlled by the CoARA secretariat, and while it is publicly available, it is not under the control of the EOSC Track project for redistribution or persistent archival.

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

As such, the dataset is reused internally under its existing license and availability terms, and no FAIRification or PID registration is applied by EOSC Track. The source is cited and referenced via its original URL for transparency and traceability.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

CoARA Signatories Dataset

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Closed

The dataset is marked as Closed because it is owned and maintained by the CoARA secretariat. Due to legal and ownership restrictions, the project is not permitted to share, modify, or redistribute the dataset. As such, no part of the dataset will be made openly available or stored in EOSC Track repositories.

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

The dataset (CoARA signatories list) will not be redistributed or archived as a standalone public output by EOSC Track, due to ownership and licensing constraints. During the project, the dataset will be accessed directly from the official CoARA web (or from the CoARA Secretariat).

After the EOSC Track project ends, access to this data will continue via the original source (CoARA website). EOSC Track outputs that use or reference this data—such as indicators or visualizations in the EOSC Open Science Observatory—will remain accessible via the Observatory.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

The datasets deposited in open repositories (Zenodo) will be preserved for long-term access. This ensures that the data remains accessible and usable beyond the duration of the project.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

No

Metadata will not be provided for the described dataset, as the data is owned and maintained by the CoARA secretariat and reused under conditions that limit redistribution and secondary exposure. EOSC Track accesses the data solely for internal analysis and reference within project outputs and does not publish or host either the dataset or its metadata.

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET/OUTPUT?

No

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

No licence will be assigned by EOSC Track for this dataset. As stated above, the data originates from the CoARA and is curated and owned by the CoARA secretariat. EOSC Track only reuses the data under the conditions provided by CoARA and does not redistribute or relicense it.

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

No

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

0 Euro

No cost is associated with making this dataset FAIR, as the EOSC Track project does not undertake FAIRification activities for this dataset. The data are owned and maintained by the CoARA secretariat and reused under their terms. EOSC Track uses the data internally and does not generate metadata, assign a licence, or share the dataset, thus incurring no FAIR-related expenses.

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

No costs

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

Tereza Szybisty (Simova) (orcid:0000-0002-1774-4335)

Tereza Szybisty (Simova) is EOSC Track project manager, responsible for overall implantation of DMP.

5.1 Data Security

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

unknown

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.2 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

Conclusion

The DMP for the EOSC Track project outlines the strategies and procedures for managing the data generated, collected, and processed throughout the project's duration. The DMP ensures that all research data are managed according to best practices, facilitating their accessibility, preservation, and reuse. This is the second, updated version of the DMP. It has been created using the ARGOS service (<https://argos.openaire.eu>). Through this DMP, the EOSC Track project is committed to maintaining high standards of data management, thereby supporting the principles of open science and the EOSC initiative.